

Ion Activity Products of $\text{AlPO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $\text{FePO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ in Acid Soils

Part I. Single Extraction of Soils with Neutral Salt Solutions of Different Ionic Strengths.

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Ionic activity products of variscite, $\text{AlPO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and strengite, $\text{FePO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ have been computed in some Indian acid soils on the basis of the general formula $\text{M}(\text{OH})_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{PO}_4$, where M stands for Fe^{3+} or Al^{3+} by extracting the soils with KCl , $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$ and CaCl_2 solutions of two ionic strengths 0.02 and 0.04. Satisfactory results have been obtained for the pK_{sp} . [$-\log$ (solubility product)] values of these phosphates in different soils at different pH ranges. The variation of pK_{sp} values with pH observed has been explained.

ACID soils contain sesquioxides of Al and Fe in appreciable amounts and it has been suggested that phosphate in acid soils exists mostly as well-defined Fe and Al phosphates of low solubility³. If this is so, these Fe and Al phosphates should exhibit solubility characteristics, such as ionic activity products, the constancy or otherwise of which may give some insight into the nature of these phosphates. The phosphates particularly studied by Jackson and coworkers^{5,6,9}, Hemwall⁸ and Chakravarti and Talibudeen⁴ with reference to this concept are variscite, $\text{AlPO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and strengite, $\text{FePO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ of general formula $\text{M}(\text{OH})_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{PO}_4$ where M stands for Fe^{3+} or Al^{3+} . The scope of formation of these phosphates in acid soils has been studied here on the basis of the solubility product concept using neutral salt solutions of low ionic strengths for the extraction of phosphates from soils.

Experimental

Three different extractant solutions of 1-1, 1-2 and 2-1 electrolytes, e.g., KCl , $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$ and CaCl_2 , and ionic strengths 0.02 and 0.04 have been used here. Five grams of soil, 500 ml of the extracting solution and about 1 ml of chloroform (added to prevent microbial activity) were shaken for 10 days for equilibrium. The pH of the suspension was then measured using a glass electrode and the Cambridge pH-meter, and Al, Fe and phosphate concentrations determined colorimetrically in the filtrate using the modified Truog and Meyer¹³ method for phosphate and the methods of Peech and English¹⁰ for Al and Fe.

Treatment of data :

Negative logarithms of the ionic activity products of $\text{AlPO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $\text{FePO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ have been computed on the basis of the general equation :

so that

$$K_{sp} = [\text{M}^{3+}][\text{H}_2\text{PO}_4^-][\text{OH}^-]^2$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} \text{pK}_{sp} &= -\log K_{sp} = \text{p}[\text{M}^{3+}] + \text{p}[\text{H}_2\text{PO}_4^-] + 2\text{p}[\text{OH}^-] \\ &= \text{p}[\text{M}^{3+}] + \text{p}[\text{H}_2\text{PO}_4^-] + 2\text{pK}_w \\ &\quad - 2\text{pH} \end{aligned}$$

where M^{3+} stands for Fe^{3+} or Al^{3+} , K_w for the ionic product of water and the figures in square brackets represent the activities of the corresponding ionic species⁶.

Computation of the pK_{sp} values according to the above equations requires (a) the fraction (or percentage) of the total phosphate present as H_2PO_4^- ions at different pH values, and (b) the fraction of the total Fe and Al present as Fe^{3+} and Al^{3+} at different pH values.

Percentages of total phosphate present as H_2PO_4^- at different ionic media were calculated using the first and second ionisation constants, K_I° & K_{II}° , of H_3PO_4 as given by Bjerrum and Unmack¹ in a medium of zero strength,

$$\text{pK}_I^\circ = 2.120 + 0.0059(t - 18^\circ\text{C})$$

$$\text{pK}_{II}^\circ = 7.228 - 0.0033(t - 18^\circ\text{C})$$

and the Debye-Huckel relation connecting activity coefficient with ionic strength. If K_1 be the first ionisation constant of H_3PO_4 in a medium of ionic strength, μ , one gets (neglecting the other stages of ionisation),

$$\text{K}_1 = \frac{[\text{H}^+][\text{H}_2\text{PO}_4^-]}{[\text{H}_3\text{PO}_4]}$$

and hence

$$\%H_2PO_4^- = \frac{100K_I}{K_I + [H^+]}$$

where $[H^+]$ is the H^+ ion activity as obtained from pH.

Similarly, from

$$K_{II} = \frac{[H^+][HPO_4^-]}{[H_2PO_4^-]}$$

One gets, by neglecting the other stages of ionisation,

$$\%H_2PO_4^- = \frac{100[H^+]}{[H^+] + K_{II}}$$

The percentages of Fe^{3+} and Al^{3+} at different pH's were obtained from the first stage of hydrolysis of M^{3+} (neglecting the other stages),

so that

$$K = \frac{[M(OH)^{2+}]}{[M^{3+}][OH^-]}$$

This gives the percentage of total M present as M^{3+} in a solution of ionic strength 0.02.

$$\%M^{3+} = \frac{100 \times 2.04[H^+]}{2.04[H^+] + K} \times \text{total M}$$

where K stands for the first hydrolysis constant. The values of K used in the present work were

$$\text{for } Fe^{3+} \text{ } K = 6.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ at } 25^\circ,^{2,12}$$

and,

$$\text{for } Al^{3+} \text{ } K = 7.76 \times 10^{-6} \text{ at } 25^\circ.^{11}$$

A. *Extractants of different ionic strengths :*

Three different Indian acid soils M (Midnapore, alluvial), P (Purulia, sandy loam) and C (Cinchona soil from Munsong, Darjeeling) were extracted with KCl, $(NH_4)_2SO_4$ and $CaCl_2$ solutions of ionic strengths 0.02 and 0.04. The data are given in Tables 1A and 1B below :

It is noticeable that although the pH values change slightly with change in ionic strength, a higher ionic strength corresponding to a lower pH as expected⁷, the pK_{sp} values remain more or less constant due to

TABLE 1A—NEGATIVE LOGARITHMS OF THE IONIC PRODUCT (pK_{sp} VALUES) OF IRON AND ALUMINIUM PHOSPHATE OF ACID SOILS IN SOLUTIONS OF DIFFERENT IONIC STRENGTHS

Soil No.	Solution	pH	P $M \times 10^6$	pH_2PO_4	Fe $M \times 10^6$	pFe^{3+}	Al $M \times 10^6$	pAl^{3+}	pK_{sp} $FePO_4 \cdot 2H_2O$	pK_{sp} $AlPO_4 \cdot 2H_2O$
<i>Ionic strength 0.02</i>										
M-1	0.02M KCl	5.72	4.00	5.41	0.21	9.86	11.82	5.38	31.82	27.35
	0.0067M $CaCl_2$	5.62	4.00	5.41	0.21	9.77	6.00	5.63	31.94	27.80
	0.0067M $(NH_4)_2SO_4$	5.76	3.00	5.54	0.35	9.67	3.11	6.11	31.69	28.13
P-1	0.02M KCl	5.94	4.00	5.47	0.21	10.10	3.10	6.14	31.69	27.73
	0.0067M $CaCl_2$	6.10	2.60	5.62	0.67	9.74	1.10	6.72	31.16	28.14
	0.0067M $(NH_4)_2SO_4$	6.20	3.00	5.57	2.10	9.35	2.12	6.53	30.52	27.70
C-4	0.02M KCl	3.95	3.90	5.41	3.40	7.86	51.30	4.30	33.37	29.81
	0.0067M $CaCl_2$	4.08	1.00	6.00	2.25	7.21	65.55	4.20	33.05	30.04
	0.0067M $(NH_4)_2SO_4$	4.50	2.31	5.64	1.75	1.75	42.71	4.42	32.37	29.08

TABLE 1B

Ionic strength 0.04

M-1	0.04M KCl	5.50	4.00	5.40	0.42	9.26	14.72	5.12	31.66	27.52
	0.0134M $CaCl_2$	5.46	1.61	5.80	0.57	9.07	9.00	5.31	31.95	28.19
	0.0134M $(NH_4)_2SO_4$	5.62	4.10	5.40	0.42	9.36	6.00	5.57	31.52	27.73
P-1	0.04M KCl	6.00	6.45	5.20	1.20	9.28	1.10	6.56	30.48	27.76
	0.0134M $CaCl_2$	6.14	1.10	5.96	0.30	10.02	9.00	5.78	31.70	27.46
	0.0134M $(NH_4)_2SO_4$	6.08	4.00	5.40	0.15	10.27	6.00	5.88	30.60	26.81
C-4	0.04M KCl	4.00	3.81	5.42	3.20	6.87	51.10	4.30	32.39	29.72
	0.0134M $CaCl_2$	4.15	0.85	6.07	2.00	7.11	64.80	4.20	32.88	29.97
	0.0134M $(NH_4)_2SO_4$	4.38	2.40	5.62	2.11	7.42	43.20	4.40	32.28	29.26

establishment of equilibrium among the different ionic species, M^{3+} , H^+ (or OH^-) and H_2PO_4^- . Statistical analysis of the data are given in Table 2.

TABLE 2

pH	No. of soils	Ionic strengths	$\text{FePO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	$\text{AlPO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$
5.01-6.20	6	0.02	31.47 ± 0.33	27.81 ± 0.30
5.01-6.14	6	0.04	31.32 ± 0.55	27.58 ± 0.45

B. Extractants of same ionic strength :

Twenty four samples of acid soils were chosen for this part of the experiment. The pH's of soils showed higher values with $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$ but lower values with CaCl_2 . The changes in pH are caused by the liberation of H^+ ions by the cations of the added electrolyte. Ca^{2+} being doubly charged should liberate larger amount of H^+ than the monovalent cations and hence a greater lowering of pH is

are capable of extracting different amounts of iron, aluminium and phosphate from soils do not change the pK_{sp} values to an appreciable extent. The ionic activity products thus remain more or less constant at a particular pH, as required by the solubility product principle.

The pK_{sp} values are however seen to decrease almost linearly with rise of pH. A $\text{pK}_{sp} : \text{pH}$ graph can be drawn within the limits of the maximum and minimum values obtained by Chakravarti and Talibudeen⁴ with British and Indian soils. The decrease in pK_{sp} values with rise of pH may be due to—

- (i) over-estimation of the activities of the trivalent cations Fe^{3+} and Al^{3+} on the basis of their known hydrolysis constants; this may lead to considerable variation of results particularly above pH, 5.5, and
- (ii) formation of smaller metal phosphate crystals of greater solubility at pH values higher than the isoelectric point, the optimum pH for the formation of well-defined crystals.

TABLE 3

Soil	0.02M KCl	0.0067M $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$	0.0067M CaCl_2	Soil	0.02M KCl	0.0067M $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$	0.0067M CaCl_2
B-1	4.70	4.85	4.36	B-7	5.24	5.37	4.80
B-2	5.93	5.92	5.41	B-8	5.22	5.36	4.72
B-3	4.86	5.18	4.56	B-9	4.46	4.61	4.12
B-4	4.56	4.56	4.10	B-10	4.62	4.74	4.38
B-5	4.80	5.38	4.93	B-11	4.70	4.60	4.17
B-6	5.70	5.31	4.84	B-12	4.88	5.54	4.85

expected. The order of replacement of H^+ ions generally follows the lyotropic series. The following table gives the result of change in pH values with twelve soils. These soils from Birbhum, West Bengal, belong to the family of lateritic and Bengal Gondwana (rocky).

 TABLE 4
0.02M KCl

pH-range	No. of soils	$\text{FePO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	$\text{AlPO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$
(a) 3.87-4.40	6	32.97 ± 0.41	29.96 ± 0.46
(b) 4.41-5.00	12	33.88 ± 0.31	30.16 ± 0.33
(c) 5.01-5.93	5	32.18 ± 0.59	28.61 ± 0.65
0.0067M $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$			
(a) 4.42-5.00	11	33.00 ± 0.79	29.59 ± 0.51
(b) 5.04-5.93	11	32.28 ± 0.68	28.81 ± 0.62
0.0067M CaCl_2			
(a) 3.96-4.80	17	33.48 ± 0.41	30.84 ± 0.71
(b) 4.84-5.62	6	33.02 ± 0.43	29.36 ± 0.42

These results point out clearly that different extracting solutions of the same ionic strength 0.02 which

The pK_{sp} values presented here are in good accord with the results obtained by previous workers⁴.

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